

Sanctuary at Tell Damiyah

also known as “Tell Damiyah”, “Tell ed-Damieh”, “Tell Damiya”, “تل داميا”

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Entry tags: Canaanite Religions, Religious Group, Religious Practice, Syro-Palestinian Religion, Levantine Religion

Tell Damiyah, a small settlement mound overlooking the confluence of the Jordan and Zerqa rivers, is the location of a late Iron Age building (ca. 700 BCE) with evidence for various Iron Age religious practices and artefacts. Hence, it was interpreted as a sanctuary. It is difficult to ascertain which deity/deities were worshipped here due to the lack of written data or and/or for example statues of deities. There is, however, potential evidence for the cult of Asherah/Astarte. Among religious objects encountered in and around the sanctuary building are anthropomorphic ceramic statues and both zoomorphic and anthropomorphic figurines, and the building itself contained two separate altars/podia. Exactly which Iron Age kingdom (e.g. Israel, Judah or Ammon), if any, Tell Damiyah belonged to remains ambiguous, although ceramic traditions from nearby contemporary sites such as Tell Deir 'Alla point to closer contact with the region of Ammon, rather than the areas west of the Jordan River.

Date Range: 850 BCE - 700 BCE

Region: Tell Damiyah

Region tags: Middle East, Levant, Jordan, Jordan Valley

Location of a small settlement mound called 'Tell Damiyah', located in the innermost part of the Jordan Valley, near the confluence of the Jordan and Zerqa (Biblical Jabbok) Rivers.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Petit, L. P., and Z. Kafafi, 2016. Beyond the River Jordan: a Late Iron Age Sanctuary at Tell Damiyah. *Near Eastern Archaeology* 79(1), 18-26.
- Source 2: Petit, L. P., and Z. Kafafi, forthcoming. Religious Behaviour at Tell Damiya during the Late Iron Age. In: J. Kamlah and M. Witte (eds.), *Sacred Architecture in Ancient Palestine from the Bronze Age to Medieval Times*. ADPV 49. Wiesbaden: Harrasowitz.
- Source 3: Halbertsma, D. J. H., forthcoming. Worshippers, Travellers, and Trade: the Tell Damiyah 'Sanctuary' in its Context. In L. P. Petit and Z. Kafafi (eds.), *Tell Damiyah. The 2004-2019 Seasons. Papers on Archaeology of the Leiden Museum of Antiquities*. Leiden: Sidestone Press.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.rmo.nl/en/research/excavations/tell-damiyah/>

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Israelite Religions, Arabian Religions, Transjordanian Religions, Assyrian Religions (possibly)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As it is unclear what specific cultural group, if any, Tell Damiyah belonged to, this remains difficult to answer. What the archaeological record does reflect, is that multiple cultural influences coexisted within the religious building's daily functioning.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As it is unclear what specific cultural group, if any, Tell Damiyah belonged to, this remains difficult to answer. What the archaeological record does reflect, is that multiple cultural influences coexisted within the religious building's daily functioning.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As it is unclear what specific cultural group, if any, Tell Damiyah belonged to, this remains difficult to answer. What the archaeological record does reflect, is that multiple cultural influences coexisted within the religious building's daily functioning.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the Tell Damiyah religious building was destroyed in a sudden conflagration, it is as yet unclear whether this was accidental or intentional, or even if it was caused by for example an earthquake.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the Tell Damiyah religious building was destroyed in a sudden conflagration, it is as yet unclear whether this was accidental or intentional, or even if it was caused by for example an earthquake. Of particular interest here, is that Tell Damiyah might be mentioned in the victory stele of pharaoh Shoshenq I at Karnak, where the site might be listed, transliterated, as 'idmi'. It is mentioned in a list of places Shoshenq I visited/destroyed during his military campaign in Israel and Judah, around the late 10th century BCE. Shoshenq I mentioned four settlements that were captured in the Central Jordan Valley region, linked to the Biblical cities of Adamah, Succoth, Penuel and Mahanaim (Petit 2012, 201). During the course of this campaign, on his way north along the western bank of the Jordan River, he sent out "a second sizeable 'task-force' which in turn sped down Wadi el Far'a, crossed the Jordan by the ford at Adam(ah)" (Kitchen 1973, 298).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is as yet unclear whether Tell Damiyah belonged to any specific cultural group, if any, making it difficult to approach this based solely on the archaeological evidence.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is as yet unclear whether Tell Damiyah belonged to any specific cultural group, if any, making it difficult to approach this based solely on the archaeological evidence.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religion have official political support

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The presence of a bulla inscribed with cuneiform indicates far-reaching trade contacts with the

Assyrian sphere of influence, yet this is hardly evidence for political support.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While Tell Damiyah, if seen as an independently functioning shrine, must be seen as a small settlement housing no more than several households due to its size, it is as yet unclear whether or not it belonged to any particular cultural group from the wider region (e.g. Israelite, Ammonite, Edomite, Moabite). What is clear, is that the archaeological record reflects Tell Damiyah's inhabitants had ongoing interaction with many of these cultural groups, and hence might have seen adherents of religious groups of several or each of them.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While Tell Damiyah, if seen as an independently functioning shrine, must be seen as a small settlement housing no more than several households due to its size, it is as yet unclear whether or not it belonged to any particular cultural group from the wider region (e.g. Israelite, Ammonite, Edomite, Moabite). What is clear, is that the archaeological record reflects Tell Damiyah's inhabitants had ongoing interaction with many of these cultural groups, and hence might have seen adherents of religious groups of several or each of them. Here, due to the size of Tell Damiyah, it is likely that the entire settlement was involved with the daily functioning of the sanctuary building.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral

scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No formal texts have been found at Tell Damiyah

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: While small in size compared to well-known monumental religious buildings from this period, the Tell Damiyah sanctuary complex stands out as quite substantial among contemporary buildings in the Jordan Valley.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 40

Notes: It is likely that the sanctuary building was quite substantial in size, existing of several adjoined rooms forming a larger complex. Given the small size of the tell's summit, this complex would have covered a significant area of the summit.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the sanctuary room measures ca. 10.6 x 4.2 m., the exact size of the larger building complex is as yet unknown, but likely no less than ca. 15 x 10 m.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear what the exact height of the Tell Damiyah sanctuary would have been, but the presence a single layer of roof collapse, combined with the presence of a roof-roller which had collapsed through the roof of the building, indicates that the building would likely have been only one story. Whether a superstructure existed on top of the mud-brick roof is as yet unclear.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As it is unclear what specific cultural group, if any, Tell Damiyah belonged to, this remains difficult to answer.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

Notes: Iconography was encountered in various locations across the site, such as in the street, in the sanctuary building, and in adjacent storerooms.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Two-headed horse figurines might be depictions of supernatural beings

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humans:
– Yes
Notes: Numerous examples of the well-known 'Judean Pillar Figurines' were encountered in and near the sanctuary building, as well as anthropomorphic pottery statues.
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other features of iconography:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: While this is entirely possible, and indeed common with many neighbouring cultures, it is unclear whether a supreme high god was present/worshipped at Tell Damiyah.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Several of the female figurines encountered at Tell Damiyah might point to the worship of the female deity 'Astarte' or 'Asherah'. One such figurines more likely depicts the goddess 'Hathor', and this figurine might have survived from the Early Iron Age.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Asherah or Astarte is often associated with fertility rituals, childbirth, and with the cult of a dea nutrix.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Usually associated with fertility and childbirth

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: While it is quite common in the Bible that the worship of Asherah in

conjunction with or opposed to Yahweh was prohibited and frowned upon, it is clear from the archaeological record that this did in fact take place.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the presence of two-headed horse figurines might indicate the presence of supernatural non-human beings, it is not clear if these would have always been present.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Notes: Unclear, insufficient data

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: It is theorised that engaging with figurines as for example votive offerings could win favour with the supernatural

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the strategic location of Tell Damiyah, it could be hypothesised that success on journeys crossing the Jordan River is not an unlikely reward to have been sought.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: With the cult of Astarte/Asherah, it is hypothesised that praying to this deity could win favour rewarding enhanced health for fertility, during childbirth, etc.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not enough data, though unlikely in this period

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Votive offerings are encountered within the sanctuary, such as figurines and ceramic vessels, several of which must have been quite valuable (e.g. Phoenician glass vessel).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

To other in-group members:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

To out-groups:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Destroyed:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Other:

– Yes [specify]: These offerings/sacrifices might have been made to the deity/deities worshipped at Tell Damiyah.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Difficult to approach through the archaeological record

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: The presence of animal bones around the sanctuary, votive and libation offerings, point to shared activities such as 'large-scale' rituals (though likely not in the traditional sense, due to the modest dimensions of the sanctuary building).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of

governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: It is as yet unclear whether Tell Damiyah was formally incorporated into any specific society, but if it was a state is the most likely candidate (e.g. states like Israel, Judah, Ammon, Moab, Edom).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Notes: Large presence of stored grains in storeroom might have served travellers

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient data

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of a cuneiform bulla shows an engagement, however small, with the bureaucratic system of the Assyrian empire.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While significant food storage was encountered in two storerooms near the sanctuary, it is unclear whether these were public or controlled.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the strategic location of Tell Damiyah, just before/across one of the few fords over the Jordan River, it is possible that sanctuary was provided here to people travelling east-west across the Jordan Valley.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is as yet unclear, although it is possible that the sanctuary managed to stay in existence due to such a system of taxes or tithes in exchange for religious favour.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Several ancient North-West Semitic scripts, Cuneiform.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: It is likely trading was also an important part of Tell Damiyah's subsistence economy.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)